

1 **Root growth compensates for molar wear in adult goats (*Capra aegagrus hircus*)**

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23 **ABSTRACT**

24 One reason for the mammalian clade's success is the evolutionary diversity of their teeth. In
25 herbivores, this is represented by high crowned teeth evolved to compensate for wear caused
26 by dietary abrasives like phytoliths and grit. Exactly how dietary abrasives wear teeth is still
27 not fully understood. We fed four different pelleted diets of increasing abrasiveness (lucerne L;
28 grass G; grass and rice husks GR; grass, rice husks and sand GRS) to four groups of a total of
29 28 adult goats, all with fully erupted third molars, over a six-month period. Tooth morphology
30 was captured by medical CT scans at the beginning and end of the controlled feeding
31 experiment, and separation lines between the crown and root segments were defined in the
32 upper right M2, to gauge absolute wear. Using bootstrapping, significant differences in volume
33 loss between diets L/G and GR/GRS were detected. A small but nevertheless consistent volume
34 gain was noted in the roots, and there was a significant, positive correlation between crown
35 volume loss and root volume gain. This growth could possibly be attributed to the well-known
36 process of cementum deposition and its relation with a putative feedback mechanism, in place
37 to attenuate wear caused by abrasive diets.

38

39 **KEYWORDS**

40 Controlled feeding experiment, 3D imaging, ruminant teeth, dental wear, tooth volume,
41 cementum

42

43 **RESEARCH HIGHLIGHTS**

- 44 • Long term feeding experiment was performed with adult goats, in order to
45 establish how different abrasives affect tooth crown volume.
- 46 • After six months on different experimental diets, crown volume loss showed
47 significant differences according to diet abrasiveness.
- 48 • Although in ruminants teeth growth is considered finite, we recorded an increase
49 in root volume proportional to the loss of crown tissue, possibly suggesting a
50 compensatory mechanism.

51

52 **GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT**

53

54 Relationship between crown tissue-loss (wear) and root tissue-gain (growth) of the upper
55 secondary molar in adult goats (*Capra aegagrus hircus*) (n=26), fed diets of different
56 abrasiveness for six months. L lucerne, G grass, GR grass/rice husks, GRS grass/rice
57 husks/sand. As indicated by tooth symbols: the more crown is worn away, the more
58 cementum is deposited on the roots.

59 **1 INTRODUCTION**

60 Teeth are a prime representation of evolution, in which the varying dental morphologies of
61 vertebrates have adapted to cope with diverse diets. In this view, the adaptation of mammalian
62 teeth is one of the main reasons for their evolutionary success (Reilly et al., 2001). Mammalian
63 teeth are mainly composed of dentin, covered by enamel in the crown and by cementum in the
64 roots. A pulp canal runs through the hollow inside of the tooth, accommodating the nerves and
65 vessels that supply the dentine core (Ungar, 2010). Whether teeth are brachydont (low-
66 crowned) or hypsodont (high-crowned) depends on crown height and tooth width (Van Valen,
67 1960). This can also be determined by observing the junction between the root and the crown,
68 though determining where the enamel and dentin layers end and where the cementum begins is
69 not always clear, especially for hypsodont teeth. In many species of rodents or lagomorphs,
70 teeth may be rootless and thus throughout the lifetime of the individual; these are referred to as
71 euhyposodont teeth (Hillson, 1986; Koenigswald, 2011).

72 Hypsodonty has evolved and increased in proportion over time (Jernvall and Fortelius,
73 2002; Samuels and Hopkins, 2017) as a response to high amounts of wear on the dental tissue
74 related to the ingested diet (Damuth and Janis, 2011; Janis and Fortelius, 1988), where the two
75 main factors causing wear are phytoliths and grit (Damuth and Janis, 2011; Toljagić et al., 2018;
76 Williams and Kay, 2001). Grass contains more phytoliths (hard opaline silicates) than browse
77 (Hodson et al., 2005; Sanson et al., 2007). As phytoliths are thought to cause wear shaping the
78 pattern of tooth facet development (Kaiser et al., 2013), it could facilitate discrimination
79 between grazers and browsers based on the tooth wear pattern. Ruminants with a diet mainly
80 composed of grasses often have high crowned teeth (Simpson, 1955; Williams and Kay, 2001).
81 Due to their lower feeding height compared with browsers, grazers also tend to ingest soil
82 abrasives along with plant matter, further increasing tooth wear (Damuth and Janis, 2011; Janis
83 and Fortelius, 1988). However, exactly how much internal or external abrasives contribute to
84 wear, and how long this takes, is still under debate (Baker et al., 1959; Lucas et al., 2013;
85 Mainland, 2003; Sanson et al., 2007; Xia et al., 2015).

86 Wear caused by both, internal and external abrasives, can be observed at different levels.
87 Microscopic wear (e.g., dental microwear texture (Grine, 1986; Scott et al., 2005; Ungar et al.,
88 2003) and 3D surface texture (Calandra and Merceron, 2016)) measures complex topographic
89 features on the tooth's surface, deemed to represent an animals' diet over the last few days
90 (Percher et al., 2018; Schulz et al., 2013; Scott et al., 2005; Teaford and Oyen, 1989b; Ungar et
91 al., 2007). On a macroscopic level, wear is described by mesowear (Fortelius and Solounias,
92 2000) scoring occlusal relief and cusp shape of the tooth ectoloph in order to reconstruct an
93 animal's diet; it is thought to represent more of an average lifetime signal (Ackermans et al.,
94 2018; Brent Jones and Desantis, 2017; Merceron et al., 2007; Yamada, 2012).

95 Precisely quantifying tooth wear by observing loss of dental tissue on a macroscopic
96 scale is difficult. The established method to quantify species- or population-specific volume
97 loss is to measure crown height of a series of teeth from individuals that died at various ages
98 and, based on this, estimate a wear rate used to characterize the population. These estimated
99 rates have been generated for many species (reviewed in Damuth and Janis, 2014) but recently,
100 more modern techniques are able to provide exact information on volume loss in experimental
101 conditions, using 3D imaging techniques (Karme et al., 2016). Our approach here consists of
102 using 3D volume analysis of computer tomography image stacks to define the absolute loss of
103 dental tissue over time, and determine the relation to different diets.

104 Diet-related differences in dental wear have been reported experimentally in a range of
105 species, including goats (*Capra aegagrus hircus*, Linnaeus 1758) (Ackermans et al., 2018;
106 Solounias et al., 2014), rabbits (*Oryctolagus cuniculus* Linnaeus 1758) (Müller et al., 2014),
107 guinea pigs (*Cavia porcellus* Linnaeus 1758) (Müller et al., 2015) and vervet monkeys
108 (*Chlorocebus pygerythrus* Cuvier 1821) (Teaford and Oyen, 1989a). Concerning external
109 abrasives, fine dust has been suggested to create a volume loss effect without affecting the
110 macroscopic mesowear pattern (Kaiser et al., 2013), and in experimental microwear studies on
111 sheep (*Ovis aries* Linnaeus 1758) in which fine dust (<100 µm) was added to forage, Merceron
112 et al. (2007) noted little effect of the extrinsic dust on microwear. Additionally, when adding

113 sand to experimental diets, Hoffman et al. (2015) observed microwear pitting for medium grain-
114 sized silica sand (250-425 μ m), but no grit-effect was evident when smaller fine-grained silica
115 sand (180-250 μ m) was added. Large-grained sand originating from ingested soil, on the other
116 hand, creates severe, even pathological tissue loss, often reshaping wear-facets entirely. This
117 was first described in New Zealand sheep where high wear, recorded as incisor volume loss,
118 was related to soil ingestion on very eroded pastures (Barnicoat, 1957; Healy, 1967; Ludwig et
119 al., 1966; Madden, 2014), and also seen in zoo animals feeding on sandy soils (Martin Jurado
120 et al., 2008). In small mammals, as part of the experiments mentioned above (Müller et al.,
121 2014; Müller et al., 2015), diets containing coarse sand resulted in larger amounts of tooth loss
122 on incisors and cheek teeth than the same diet without added sand. Using these same diets in
123 an *in vitro* study on horse molars subjected to mechanical standardized chewing, Karme et al.
124 (2016) found the added sand diet to cause the most volume loss when observed with a μ CT.

125 In a previous publication (Ackermans et al., 2018) we reported mesowear signal
126 development in goats during a controlled feeding experiment over six months. Additional 3D
127 data from this study was employed here to report total tooth volume of the upper right M2 of
128 26 adult female goats using computed-tomographic (CT) imaging and 3D visualization, in order
129 to record variations in tooth volume over time in relation to diets of increasing abrasiveness.
130 Tooth crown volume is expected to decrease according to the abrasiveness of the diet, i.e. the
131 group fed the most abrasive diet (GRS>GR>G>L) is expected to show the most absolute
132 volume loss.

133 2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

134 2.1 Animals

135 Animal experiments were performed with approval of the Swiss Cantonal Animal Care and Use
136 Committee Zurich (animal experiment licence N° 115/2009). Twenty-eight adult female
137 domestic goats (*Capra aegagrus hircus*, Linnaeus 1758) of mixed breeds and varying ages
138 (Saanen goats, Chamois coloured goats and Toggenburger goats; average body mass = 60 ± 8
139 kg, estimated age = 3-10 years, exact ages unknown but all with erupted third molars) were
140 acquired from various sources across Switzerland, though exact birth dates are unknown, as
141 acquiring non-pregnant registered breeding stock of the desired age was beyond the limitations
142 of our study. The animals were divided randomly into four groups, consisting of seven
143 individuals each, and kept in an indoor stable (40 m² per group) covered by industrial carpet,
144 with access to a concreted outdoor compartment (12 m² per group). The feeding experiment
145 was 182 to 198 days long for 24 of the animals, as euthanasia had to be staggered to facilitate
146 a detailed dissection of each animal for further research; and from 107 to 176 days long for four
147 other animals that were euthanised before the end of the experiment due to reasons unrelated to
148 the study. At the end of the experimental period the animals were slaughtered and the skulls
149 were skeletonised by enzymatic maceration at the Center of Natural History, University of
150 Hamburg, where they are permanently curated in the Mammalogy Collection.

151

152 2.2 Diets

153 Experimental diets were designed to contain different levels and types of abrasives between
154 groups, with abrasiveness increasing from lucerne pellets (L), grass pellets (G) to grass pellets
155 with rice husks (GR) and grass pellets with rice husks with an addition of sand (GRS;
156 playground sand, grain size 0–1 mm, REDSUN garden products B.V., Heijen, Denmark; mean
157 particle size measured by sieve analysis of 0.233 mm). These diets were of the same batch as
158 those used in experiments with rabbits (Müller et al., 2014), guinea pigs (Müller et al., 2015)
159 and in vitro with horse teeth (Karme et al., 2016). The pelleted diets were designed so the

160 proportion of indigestible silica abrasives in the GRS diet was mimicked by a similar proportion
161 of indigestible, non-abrasive filler (pure lignocellulose, Arbocel, JRS Pharma, Rosenberg,
162 Switzerland) and soybean meal in the other diets, to ensure comparable levels of energy and
163 nutrients per amount of pellets (Müller et al., 2014). Grass hay was provided to all groups except
164 for the lucerne group, which was fed lucerne hay. Each animal received 1500 g of pelleted food
165 and 100 g of hay daily. It should be noted that in this experiment the diets were designed to
166 mainly comprise pellets, and the provided proportion of hay was therefore lower than the
167 normal forage ration for ruminants. Water was available for *ad libitum* consumption at all times.
168 Samples of all diet items and faecal samples of all animals before slaughter were analysed for
169 acid-detergent insoluble ash (ADIA) as a measure for silica (abrasives) content (Hummel et al.,
170 2011); a nutritional analysis of the pelleted diets and the silica concentrations have been
171 reported previously (Ackermans et al., 2018; Müller et al., 2014).

172

173 **2.3 Computer tomography**

174 Computed tomography images were acquired from a helical multislice Siemens scanner
175 (Siemens Medical Solutions, Erlangen, Germany) housed at University of Zurich Veterinary
176 Hospital. Throughout the experiment, parameters were kept constant: tube voltage at 120 kVp,
177 image matrix of 512 x 512 pixels, field of view of 980 x 332 pixels, slice thickness of 0.6 mm
178 and B60s convolution kernel. At the start of the experiment, before being assigned to the
179 experimental diets, the animals were CT scanned in order to have a baseline for the tooth
180 condition upon arrival. Another CT scan was performed at the end of the experiment, post-
181 mortem. As is general procedure for CT scans, general anaesthesia was achieved by
182 administering ketamine, 10 mg/kg (Ketonarkon[®], Streuli Pharma AG, Uznach, Switzerland)
183 and xylazine 0.1 mg/kg (Xylazin Streuli, Streuli Pharma AG, Uznach, Switzerland)
184 intramuscularly. Anaesthesia was maintained with isoflurane (Attane[®], Provet AG, Lyssach,
185 Switzerland) mixed in oxygen with a facemask.

186 Following data acquisition, the CT datasets were converted to DICOM medical imaging
187 format and rendered into 3D surface models using Amira 5.6 (Mercury Computer Systems/3D
188 Viz group, San Diego, CA) 3D visualisation software and using Horos v3.0.1 (Horos Project
189 2015) for additional visualization.

190 Using orthographic CT slices at a dorso-ventral projection through the upper right M2
191 and proceeding apically through the image stack, three landmarks at different levels in the tooth
192 were considered as planes of division of the crown-root border (Fig. 1). Crown-segment 1 was
193 defined as the volume between the tip of the crown and crown point 1 (C1), set at the coronal–
194 most junction of the inner pulp cavity with the dentin (three visible cavities). Crown-segment
195 2 was from the tip of the crown to crown point 2 (C2), set at the slice before separation of the
196 central pulp cavity (one visible cavity) into two or more root cavities, and crown-segment 3
197 was set from the tip of the crown to crown point 3 (C3), defined at the slice where distinct roots
198 became visible. For each crown point, the part of the image stack ranging from the defined
199 crown point to the root tips was defined as root-segment R1, R2 and R3, respectively. Figure 1
200 was obtained by scanning a lower left m3 (animal N° 8; the m3 was used for visualisation as it
201 was naturally loosened during maceration, wishing not to damage any other specimens) with
202 an industrial μ CT scanner (Nikon XT H 225ST) housed at the University of Zurich. Though
203 the M3 has a third cusp, the same method applies.

204 Manual thresholding of the slice images was performed so as to take the inner pulp
205 cavity of the tooth into account as part of the total volume. From this point on, the upper right
206 M2 was measured in each individual, for each of the two CT scans. The white balance was set
207 at a pixel range of -200 to 2384 pixels and the threshold was set to the full range (-1024 to
208 3071). The tooth was then delimited manually with the paintbrush tool on multiple slices and
209 interpolated in between for slices with similar morphology. All slices were then checked
210 visually for inconstancies before the final volume measurement. The total tooth volume was
211 measured, followed by an independent measurement of each section: tip of crown to C1, C1 to
212 C2, C2 to C3 and C3 to root tips. The same observer (NLA) performed all of the volume

213 measurements, blinded to the diet groups. Two animals (N^{os} 11 and 27) were excluded from
214 analysis due to artefacts during the CT process affecting the M2, resulting in a total of 26
215 animals analysed. Volume change was calculated by subtraction for all different measures,
216 resulting in data of total volume loss, $\Delta C1$, $\Delta C2$ etc. for each individual.

217

218 **2.4 Statistical analysis**

219 Because not all data were normally distributed, comparisons between treatment groups were
220 performed using ranked data and General Linear Models with Tukey's post hoc tests. For all
221 groups, and for each diet group separately, values for C1-3, R1-3 and the total volume were
222 compared between start and end using paired *t*-tests. The difference in crown tissue loss and
223 root tissue gain measurements between start and end were compared between groups using
224 ANOVA and Sidak's post hoc tests. Because post hoc tests did not always indicate significant
225 differences between groups after a significant ANOVA, the ANOVA was repeated in these
226 cases with bootstrapping (1000 bootstraps, stratified by diet, 95% confidence intervals of
227 differences), to test whether the confidence interval of the difference between groups included
228 zero. Simple correlations between measures were assessed using Pearson's *R*. The effect of
229 crown tissue loss and diet group on root tissue gain was assessed using General Linear Models
230 (GLM), confirming normal distribution of residuals, with root tissue gain as the dependent
231 variable, crown tissue loss as the independent variable, and diet as cofactor. GLM were first
232 performed including the crown tissue loss * diet interaction, but this was never significant, and
233 the GLM were repeated without the interaction. All analyses were performed in SPSS 22.0
234 (IBM, Armonk, NY, USA), with the significance level set to $P < 0.05$.

235

236 **3 RESULTS**

237 The paired *t*-test of the total M2 volume at the start vs. end of the experiment indicated a
238 significant overall decrease in volume (Table 1). This volume loss was also highly significant
239 in *t*-tests for the crown segments, regardless of the method applied, and a numerical volume

240 gain was visible for all root segments, albeit non-significant for R2 (Table 1). When accounting
241 for diet, volume loss was numerically evident, though significant in *t*-tests only for GR and
242 GRS. Specifically for diet G, $\Delta C1$ is the sole measure showing numerical loss, though non-
243 significant (Table 1). In the roots, numerical gain in volume is evident overall and significant
244 for the GR and GRS diets (Table 1).

245 Comparing the four diet groups by ANOVA (no bootstrapping), significant differences
246 were apparent for the total volume loss as well as $\Delta C1$, $\Delta C2$ and $\Delta C3$, but without subsequent
247 differences at post hoc testing (except for $\Delta C2$, where the G diet was significantly lower than
248 the other ones; Table 2). Bootstrapping also isolated diet G when observing the total volume
249 loss, $\Delta C2$ and $\Delta C3$. In contrast, L & G were significantly different from GR and GRS for $\Delta C1$
250 and for $\Delta C2$ after bootstrapping (Table 2).

251 Pearson's correlation coefficient was highest for the $\Delta C1$ - $\Delta R1$ relationship at $R=0.74$.
252 The correlations between $\Delta C2$ - $\Delta R2$ and $\Delta C3$ - $\Delta R3$ were also significant, but at decreasing *R* as
253 the separation line approached the root tips (Table 2, Fig. 1, Fig. 2). This observation was
254 confirmed using GLM (Table 4). Finally, the diet cofactor only showed a trend ($p=0.056$) in
255 the GLM using the C1/R1 approach, but not for the C2/R2 or C3/R3 approaches. The
256 relationship of $\Delta R1$ to $\Delta C1$ was additionally characterized using linear regression statistics,
257 where the resulting equation (Fig. 2) included 0 in the 95% confidence interval of the intercept
258 and 1 in the 95% confidence interval of the slope.

259 **4 DISCUSSION**

260 After six months on experimental diets, an overall volume loss was recorded in the upper right
261 M2 for the four diet groups, predominantly in the crown segment. Most interesting, a slight but
262 consistent volume gain in the root segment that was correlated to crown tissue loss was
263 observed; a finding to our knowledge which has not been reported so far in hyposodont teeth.
264 Diets higher in phytoliths led to more crown loss and root growth; surprisingly, the diet with
265 added sand (GRS) did not cause more wear than the same diet without sand (GR).

266

267 **4.1 Limitations of study design**

268 The animals used in this experiment were of variable ages and breeds, with varying tooth
269 conditions. A more homogenous sample would have been ideal. But because breeding animals
270 of the required age class are comparatively expensive (and the logistics of keeping such animals
271 until they gave birth, prior to our experiment, were considered prohibitive), and non-breeding
272 animals are mostly not kept up to the age we required for the study, we did have to accept such
273 a non-homogenous sample, although the requirement of erupted (and in-use) third molars was
274 met by all animals. Additionally, in an effort to simulate “normal” pasture conditions, the
275 amount of added grit in the GRS diet was 5%, as the average amount of soil ingested for sheep
276 ranges from 5 to 9% of daily intake, and up to 33% in extreme cases (reviewed in Damuth and
277 Janis, 2011). Incorporating sand into a pelleted diet is not an accurate representation of natural
278 forage, though consistently adding external abrasives to forage diets would have been
279 impractical over the long term. Evidently, the sand used in our experiment can not represent all
280 of the different forms of grit found in nature; nevertheless, it is a valid experimental
281 representation of a highly abrasive substrate. Finally, there can be little doubt that a pelleted
282 diet, while allowing standardized conditions over a long period of time, will evoke different
283 chewing patterns than natural forages; in particular, chewing intensity (chews per dry matter
284 intake) will be lessened on a pelleted diet (Kennedy, 1985). Therefore, it is possible that real

285 forages of similar nutrient and abrasives content would have a greater effect on tooth wear than
286 pelleted diets.

287 A further consideration is that the use of a higher resolution CT scanner would have
288 yielded more precise results and higher quality renderings; however, the necessity to scan live,
289 sedated animals only allowed for the use of a medical-grade CT scanner. Further improvements
290 may include the manual segmenting method used in the Amira 3D visualisation software, which
291 had a standard error of $\pm 200.57 \mu\text{m}^3$. An automated technique might have served to reduce this
292 error, though detecting the difference between root material and alveolar bone automatically is
293 complicated and furthermore, this technique would not have taken into account the pulp cavity
294 as part of the total volume.

295 With regards to ANOVA and bootstrapping tests (Table 2), the grass group was often
296 different to the other groups. This could be a chance finding of these particular animals having
297 higher amounts of cementum deposition, as also evident in Fig. 2.

298

299 **4.2 Absolute volume methodology**

300 The C1/R1 delineation was selected, as it appeared to be the most efficient at excluding
301 interference with root-growth (Tables 3 and 4, Fig. 2). According to the results obtained for the
302 different crown point placements, it seems as if volume gain does not only occur in the root tips
303 but also to a certain extent on the sides of the root walls, which most probably indicates lateral
304 cementum deposition e.g. as described for bison (Moffitt, 1998). In future experiments, one
305 could consider creating a permanent mark on the teeth, by drilling a small burr for example, so
306 as to define crown loss and root gain based on this mark.

307

308 **4.3 Diet**

309 Significant volume loss appeared reliably in the paired *t*-test between feeding groups on diets
310 with high phytoliths content, as in the GR and GRS diets. Using C1, GR showed the highest
311 volume loss and, contrary to expectations, GRS did not show more loss than GR, though GRS

312 contained additional external abrasives. These results correspond to findings in Ackermans et
313 al. (2018), where mesowear scored on these same goats indicated equal or slightly less wear on
314 GRS when compared with GR, which is also similar to observations by Merceron et al. (2016)
315 when observing dental microwear textures. Indeed, the absence of effect from the GRS diet can
316 be explained by the washing mechanism in place in ruminant digestion (Ackermans et al., 2018;
317 Dittmann et al., 2017; Janis et al., 2010) where large sand settles to the bottom of the rumen,
318 resulting in a less abrasive bolus upon regurgitation and therefore dampening the potential wear
319 effect of added sand on the teeth. Whether differences noted in the degree of root growth at
320 similar levels of wear, as for example evident between several animals on diets L and G (with
321 less root growth on diet L), are related to differences in the chewing load or intensity (with a
322 hypothesized lower effort on L compared with G) would have to be corroborated by further
323 experiments.

324

325 **4.4 Correlation between crown and root volume change**

326 Hypsodonty is positioned on a scale between brachydonty and euhypsodonty, with varying
327 balance between the formation of the tooth's crown and roots during the animal's life
328 (Koenigswald, 2011). In the euhypsodont incisors of rodents, the crown and roots are controlled
329 by different genetic pathways, flexible between species (Tummers and Thesleff, 2009)
330 indicating that root and crown growth may happen independently. Knowledge concerning the
331 underlying genetic factors that control euhypsodonty is most often restricted to mice and rats,
332 as they are the most accessible models in a laboratory setting, though this leads to poor
333 comprehension of tooth replacement, being that these species are monophyodont (Juuri et al.,
334 2013). The murine incisor is nevertheless the main model for hypso- and euhypsodont studies.
335 As these continuously growing teeth require persistent stem cell presence at the base of the
336 tooth, a developmental regulatory structure called the cervical loop (Jernvall and Thesleff,
337 2012; Renvoisé and Michon, 2014) promotes tooth growth there when crown material is lost to
338 wear by attrition (Harada et al., 1999).

339 The mouth contains a multitude of proprioceptors working to protect the teeth (Sanson
340 et al., 2017); periodontal ligaments for example contain mechanoreceptors that provide
341 feedback on tooth load (Hughes, 2015), at least in humans. Based on a hypothesis by Janis and
342 Fortelius (1988) that the transmission of occlusal stress from tooth to bone will pass through
343 the root to the area of root secretion, Renvoisé and Michon (2014, p. 8) hypothesize that “*the*
344 *physical forces of occlusion, dependent on the animal diet, its volume, soil grit and/or tooth*
345 *attrition, might have a mechanical effect on the tooth, and in turn, affects the stem cell niche,*
346 *through a feedback loop pathway*“. The concept of cementum growth compensating for wear
347 has been suggested by Attwell (1980, p. 121): “*as [cementum] layers are laid down throughout*
348 *life, the process may serve to continue eruption and consequently compensate for loss of crown*
349 *height resulting from tooth wear.*”, and also by Klevezal (1996, p. 4): “*molars of [...] some*
350 *ungulates are considered as evergrowing teeth. Their dentin stops growing in length rather*
351 *early but on the root cementum deposits intensively compensating to some extend [sic] the wear*
352 *of the crown*“, although neither author cited empirical data as proof for the observation. It would
353 thus not be far-fetched to imagine the existence of a tooth-specific feedback mechanism in
354 ruminants, aimed at compensating wear by inducing root growth by means of cementum
355 deposition, as suggested by our findings. The effects of such a mechanism have been shown
356 experimentally in rabbits (Meredith et al., 2015; Müller et al., 2014; Ness, 1956) and guinea
357 pigs (Müller et al., 2015), with independent growth rates between cheek teeth and incisors, and
358 there was a relation between wear and compensatory growth in the incisors and lower premolar
359 p3.

360 Camelids, suids or hippopotamids are only some examples of animals showcasing the
361 combination of molars with fixed growth and ever-growing incisors or canines, indicating the
362 possibility of euhypsodont teeth present in hypsodont animals (Koenigswald, 2011). Sequential
363 replacement in the form of delayed molar eruption is an evolutionary adaptation to wear (Janis
364 and Fortelius, 1988), although eruption timing can also be delayed by other external factors

365 such as general malnutrition or specific nutritional deficiencies (calcium and phosphorous),
366 especially in younger animals when the dentition is rapidly developing (Greenfield and Arnold,
367 2008; Moran and O'Connor, 1994; Popkin et al., 2012). Historically, tooth eruption schedules
368 for ovicaprids (reviewed by Zeder (2002)) show that molar eruption seems to follow a specific
369 time frame, with only slightly longer time periods in wild or feral animals, most likely due to
370 nutritional differences (Caughley, 1965; Silver, 1969; Taber, 1971; Vigal and Machordom,
371 1985). Still, until now, no continued growth after final eruption has been reported (Greenfield
372 and Arnold, 2008). Interestingly, seasonal deposition of cementum layers on the root area of
373 teeth has been recorded and used to age animals for many years (Laws, 1952). It is, however,
374 never described as a type of growth, even though material is clearly being added to the tooth
375 root structure.

376 Lieberman (1993) tested the effect of changes in diet on cementum microstructure in a
377 controlled feeding experiment on goats, using diets of different hardness (normal or softened
378 pellets) and with different protein, mineral (calcium and phosphorus) and vitamin content. The
379 diet hardness, before rumination, impacted cementum growth by affecting the orientation of the
380 Sharpey's fibres, which re-align to counter tensile forces that press teeth in the alveoli during
381 occlusion. This difference in orientation altered visual representation of the incremental
382 cementum lines when viewed under polarized light. The differences in diet mineralization
383 affected formation rate of collagen matrix, resulting in darker cementum bands. This
384 demonstrates that diet hardness and mineral content affect cementogenesis. In any case, growth
385 is happening at the root level, although more accurate equipment is necessary to observe
386 precisely which tissue layer of the roots is gaining volume, weather it is indeed cementum that
387 is the main source of growth in reaction to diet, and how exactly the feedback mechanism
388 works.

389

390 **5 CONCLUSION**

391 Volume changes in goat molars show the possible existence of a previously undetected
392 feedback mechanism in ruminants, possibly related to the amount of wear inflicted on the tooth,
393 which reacts and changes even in the absence of euhypsodonty. The observed increase in root
394 volume might be linked to the well-described factor of cementum deposition, already known to
395 react differently depending on various seasonal and physiological forces, though this hypothesis
396 would benefit from further physiological-based research. While this mechanism suggests itself
397 to be common to any ruminant, and even to all herbivores in which the investigation of
398 cementum deposits has been described as a method for age determination (Klevezal, 1996); the
399 spread of this mechanism across species, and for example its link to brachydonty or hypsodonty,
400 might shed further light on evolutionary adaptations to tooth wear. Following studies on
401 differential growth of individual teeth in rodents and rabbits (Ness, 1956; Schour and Medak,
402 1951), performing an experimental manipulation (a graded grinding down) of selected teeth of
403 an adult ruminant and a subsequent detailed investigation of the cementum reaction of treated
404 versus non-treated teeth might help elucidate the feedback mechanism and outline the scope
405 and limits of compensatory cementum deposition. Such approaches might be useful in
406 estimating the respective costs and constraints of the cementum deposition mechanism as
407 compared to other strategies like euhypsodonty.

408 Measuring absolute volume allows us to better understand the development of tooth
409 wear over time. Here, it confirmed that diets higher in phytoliths cause more wear, whether it
410 is recorded in the form of volume loss or mesowear, as in our previous paper, and that in
411 ruminants, large sand has little effect, probably because it is washed off the ingesta before
412 rumination.

413 Though a medical grade CT scanner was sufficient to observe slight morphological
414 changes in this study, a detailed approach into the precise mechanics of each tooth layer with a
415 higher-resolution technique should be investigated in future research.

416 The outcome of this study reveals the need to consider the implications of root growth
417 reacting to (putatively diet-specific) wear from many more points of view, including the .

418 Further research may search to tease apart how much of this signal is due to phenotypic
419 plasticity and how much is genetic. The implications for hypsodonty and euhypsodonty from
420 an evolutionary point of view are then also to be questioned. This study is a starting point, but
421 wider use of this technique will provide more information on the matter and serve to create a
422 database of tooth volume changes, of the crown and roots, which we believe will help to
423 understand dental wear immeasurably more than the technique of measuring volume on
424 ontogeneic series of teeth, used up until now.

425 In any case, teeth should be seen not as a dead structure that is just worn away, but more
426 as a part of the living, growing body.

427

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436

437 AUTHORS CONTRIBUTIONS

438 MC, TMK, DWHM, PRK and JMH designed the study, DWHM and MC performed the animal experiment,
439 ^{[[[SEP]]]}PRK supervised the CT scanning, JH supervised the nutritional analyses, NLA created the 3D renderings and
440 performed volume measurements, NLA and MC analysed the data and drafted the first version of the manuscript
441 which then received input by all other co-authors.

442

443 COMPETING INTERESTS

444 The authors declare no competing interests

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634 *Archaeozoology*, (ed. D. Ruscillio), pp. 87-118. Durham: Oxbow Books.
635
636

637 Table 1. Mean \pm SD of volume measurements in μm^3 on different crown segment (C) loss and
 638 root segment (R) gain, of the upper right M2 in goats (*Capra aegagrus hircus*) fed diets of
 639 different abrasiveness for six months.

	n	Total volume		C1		C2		C3	
		start	end	start	end	start	end	start	end
All	26	4104 ± 910	4000 $\pm 843^{**}$	2509 ± 1080	2307 $\pm 1043^{***}$	2959 ± 1057	2808 $\pm 1051^{***}$	3535 ± 1052	3392 $\pm 959^{***}$
L	6	4121 ± 1001	3982 ± 870	2585 ± 1136	2509 ± 1238	3015 ± 1118	2886 $\pm 1171^*$	3655 ± 1185	3462 $\pm 1075^*$
G	6	3742 ± 434	3793 ± 469	2352 ± 466	2256 ± 524	2577 ± 447	2652 ± 580	3193 ± 590	3227 ± 599
G/R	7	4033 ± 1028	3884 $\pm 952^*$	2642 ± 1213	2334 $\pm 1136^{***}$	2938 ± 1243	2682 $\pm 1174^{**}$	3494 ± 1251	3308 $\pm 1105^*$
G/R/S	7	4470 ± 1052	4308 $\pm 1035^*$	2444 ± 1441	2151 $\pm 1289^*$	3257 ± 1282	3001 $\pm 1306^{***}$	3766 ± 1180	3559 $\pm 1130^{**}$
	n	R1		R2		R3			
		start	end	start	end	start	end	start	end
All	26	1595 ± 764	1692 $\pm 719^*$	1145 ± 408	1191 ± 959	569 ± 379	607 $\pm 360^*$		
L	6	1536 ± 227	1473 ± 416	1106 ± 298	1095 ± 342	467 ± 223	520 ± 245		
G	6	1389 ± 228	1537 ± 217	1164 ± 223	1141 ± 256	549 ± 221	565 ± 150		
G/R	7	1391 ± 326	1550 $\pm 338^*$	1095 ± 353	1202 $\pm 336^*$	539 ± 352	577 ± 313		
G/R/S	7	2026 ± 1390	2156 ± 1229	1213 ± 667	1306 ± 735	704 ± 598	749 $\pm 582^*$		

640 Means of start and end differ significantly (paired t-test) at *** $P < 0.001$, ** $P < 0.01$, * $P < 0.05$
 641 L lucerne, G grass, G/R grass/rice husks, G/R/S grass/rice husks/sand
 642

643 Table 2. Mean differences \pm SD (95%CI) [bootstrap confidence interval] on different crown
 644 segment (C) loss and root segment (R) gain in the upper right molar M2 in μm^3 between start
 645 and end volume measurements, in goats (*Capra aegagrus hircus*) (n=26) fed diets of different
 646 abrasiveness for six months.

Measure	L	G	G/R	G/R/S
Δ Total volume*	139.5 \pm 176.7 (-45.9;325.0) [1.7; 261.9] ^B	-51.0 \pm 108.9 (-165.3; 63.3) [-132.4; 23.9] ^A	148.9 \pm 143.2 (16.5; 281.3) [53.4; 248.7] ^B	162.5 \pm 115.6 (55.5; 269.4) [87.4; 236.0] ^B
Δ C1*	76.2 \pm 176.3 (-108.8;261.2) [(-46.3;207.8)] ^A	96.5 \pm 129.8 (-39.7;232.7) [6.0;187.9] ^A	308.0 \pm 103.6 (212.2;403.8) [245.2;383.9] ^B	292.8 \pm 233.9 (76.5;509.2) [114.9;438.8] ^B
Δ C2*	129.2 \pm 118.8 ^b (4.8;253.9) [34.4; 200.5] ^B	-74.6 \pm 158.3 ^a (-240.6;91.5) [(-215.0;18.7)] ^A	255.6 \pm 105.0 ^b (158.5;352.7) [188.7; 330.8] ^C	256.0 \pm 87.0 ^b (175.6;336.4) [197.7; 310.5] ^C
Δ C3*	192.7 \pm 140.7 (45.1; 340.4) [100.4; 308.1] ^B	-34.7 \pm 96.4 (-135.9; 66.5) [-98.6; 44.9] ^A	186.4 \pm 198.8 (2.5; 370.2) [58.4; 334.3] ^B	207.4 \pm 144.3 (73.9; 340.9) [93.0; 299.4] ^B
Δ R1	-63.3 \pm 285.7 (-363.2; 236.5) [-]	147.5 \pm 149.5 (-9.4; 304.3) [-]	159.1 \pm 156.2 (14.6; 303.5) [-]	130.4 \pm 269.0 (-118.4; 379.2) [-]
Δ R2	-10.3 \pm 245.4 (-267.8; 247.3) [-]	-23.6 \pm 87.7 (-115.6; 68.4) [-]	106.7 \pm 85.4 (27.7; 185.7) [-]	93.5 \pm 119.4 (-16.9; 204.0) [-]
Δ R3	53.2 \pm 98.8 (-50.5; 156.9) [-]	16.3 \pm 134.1 (-124.5; 157.0) [-]	37.4 \pm 92.2 (-47.8; 122.7) [-]	45.0 \pm 45.2 (3.2; 86.7) [-]

647 *ANOVA $P < 0.05$

648 ^{a,b} significant differences (Sidak post hoc test) between groups

649 ^{A,B} bootstrap 95% confidence interval of difference between groups does not include zero

650 L lucerne (n=6), G grass (n=6), G/R grass/rice husks (n=7), G/R/S grass/rice husks/sand (n=7)

651

652 Table 3. Pearson's correlation coefficients between different crown segment (C) volume gain
 653 and root segment (R) volume loss in the upper right molar M2 in μm^3 crown-segment volume
 654 gain and root-segment volume loss measurements, in goats (*Capra aegagrus hircus*) (n=26)
 655 fed diets of different abrasiveness for six months.

	ΔC2	ΔC3	ΔR1	ΔR2	ΔR3
ΔC1	$R=0.56$ $P=0.003$	$R=0.28$ $P=0.170$	$R=0.74$ $P<0.001$	$R=0.50$ $P=0.009$	$R=0.26$ $P=0.195$
ΔC2		$R=0.54$ $P=0.004$	$R=0.068$ $P=0.742$	$R=0.55$ $P=0.004$	$R=0.00$ $P=0.985$
ΔC3			$R=-0.35$ $P=0.081$	$R=-0.26$ $P=0.205$	$R=0.45$ $P=0.022$
ΔR1				$R=0.66$ $P<0.001$	$R=0.28$ $P=0.165$
ΔR2					$R=0.09$ $P=0.647$

656

657

658 Table 4. Results of General Linear Models (incl. adjusted R^2) linking root tissue gain (growth)
 659 with crown tissue loss (wear), in goats (*Capra aegagrus hircus*) (n=26) fed diets of different
 660 abrasiveness for six months.

Dependent: Root growth	Model	Independent: Crown wear	Cofactor: Diet
$\Delta R1-\Delta C1$	$F_{4,21}=11.150$ $P<0.001$ $R^2=0.62$	$F_{4,21}=34.330$ $P<0.001$	$F_{3,21}=2.950$ $P=0.056$
$\Delta R2-\Delta C2$	$F_{4,21}=2.786$ $P=0.053$ $R^2=0.22$	$F_{4,21}=5.988$ $P=0.023$	$F_{3,21}=0.489$ $P=0.694$
$\Delta R3-\Delta C3$	$F_{4,21}=1.514$ $P=0.234$ $R^2=0.08$	$F_{4,21}=5.460$ $P=0.029$	$F_{3,21}=0.223$ $P=0.879$

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Figure 1. Schematic sagittal representation of three possible delimitation lines between molar crown and roots, established to measure crown and root volume in goats (*Capra aegagrus hircus*) fed diets of different abrasiveness for six months. Crown segment 1 is defined as the volume between the tip of the crown to crown point 1 (C1), and the volume from C1 to the tip of the roots is defined as root segment 1, *idem* for crown point 2 (C2) and crown point 3 (C3). White frames represent the transversal tooth-based morphology as seen on X-ray μ CT slices, used to determine the exact delimitation lines; for C1, one slice further down would show the joint pulpal cavity; for C2, one slice further down would show clearly separated pulpal cavities for the two main roots; for C3, one slice further upwards would show the cementum link between the two main roots. The tooth represented is the lower left third molar of animal N°8.

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 678 Figure 2. Relationship between crown tissue-loss (wear; using method C1) and root tissue-
 679 gain (growth, using method R1), in goats (*Capra aegagrus hircus*) (n=26) fed diets of
 680 different abrasiveness for six months. The regression equation, with 95% confidence
 681 intervals, was $y = -79 [-172;14] + 0.87 [0.54;1.21] x$ ($R^2=0.55$)
 682 L lucerne (n=6), G grass (n=6), G/R grass/rice husks (n=7), G/R/S grass/rice husks/sand (n=7)
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